

RESEARCH ON THERMOMECHANICAL PROPERTY OF WOVEN FABRIC REINFORCED SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Woven fabric reinforced shape memory polymer composites (WFRSMPCs) with high stiffnesses and high recovery forces are becoming a hot topic in the smart materials area. In the paper, the thermomechanical properties of WFRSMPCs is studied by employing the multi-scale theory to establish the microscopic model for fiber bundles (see Fig. 1) and the mesoscopic model for the WFRSMPCs (see Fig.2). As shown in Fig.1, a fiber bundle is composed of SMP matrix and fibers and can be regarded as a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite. The mesoscopic model for the WFRSMPCs is composed of SMP matrix, warp yarns and weft yarns, as shown in Fig.2. In the study, the seven-parameter generalized Maxwell model, together with the WLF equation which could be used to describe the time-temperature superposition principle, are used to characterize the viscoelastic deformation of SMP matrix. Since the viscoelastic property of the fiber bundle inherits that of the SMP matrix, relaxation moduli of the fiber bundle can be also studied in the paper. In order to analyze the effects of fiber volume fractions V and warp yarn inclination angles θ on the viscoelastic properties of the WFRSMPCs, relaxation moduli of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters are calculated in the paper, as shown in Fig. 3. It can be found that the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs along the warp fiber direction become weak with the increase of fiber volume fractions. With the increase of warp yarn inclination angles, the viscoelastic properties of WFRSMPCs along the warp fiber direction become strong first and then weak. In order to reveal the shape memory behavior of the WFRSMPCs, the strain-stress-temperature relationship during the complete free recovery of WFRSMPC with $V=50\%$ and $\theta =25^\circ$ is simulated, as shown in Fig. 4. Shape fixity ratio and shape recovery rate are two important physical quantities to describe shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs. In the study, it is found that the shape recovery rate of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters are almost equal to 100%. Further study shows the effects of process parameters on the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs. With the increase of fiber volume fractions, the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs decrease, which means the shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs become worse. With the increase of warp yarn inclination angles, the shape fixity ratio of WFRSMPCs increase first and then decrease, which means the shape memory properties of WFRSMPCs become better first and then worse. The research findings in the study could provide a basis for design and application of WFRSMPCs in engineering.

Figure 1: Internal structure of a fiber bundle

Figure 2: Internal structure of WFRSMPCs

Figure 3: Numerical simulation of Y_{11} of WFRSMPCs with different process parameters, (a) fiber volume fractions, (b) warp yarn inclination angles

Figure 4: Strain-stress-temperature graph reflecting the free recovery of WFRSMPCs

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